

Supporting Information for: Intermolecular Effects on Tunneling through Acenes in Large-area and Single-molecule Junctions

Yuru Liu,^{1,2} Luca Ornago,³ Marco Carlotti,^{1,2,4} Yong Ai,^{1,2,6} Maria El Abbassi,³ Saurabh Soni,^{1,2} Andika Asyuda,⁵ Michael Zharnikov,⁵ Herre S. J. van der Zant*³ and Ryan C. Chiechi*^{1,2}

¹*Stratingh Institute for Chemistry, University of Groningen, Nijenborgh 4, 9747 AG Groningen, the Netherlands*

²*Zernike Institute for Advanced Materials, University of Groningen, Nijenborgh 4, 9747 AG Groningen, the Netherlands*

³*Kavli Institute of Nanoscience, Delft University of Technology, Lorentzweg 1, Delft, 2628 CJ, the Netherlands*

⁴*Present address: Italian Institute of Technology, Center for MicroBioRobotics, Viale Rinaldo Piaggio 34, 56025, Pontedera, Italy*

⁵*Angewandte Physikalische Chemie, Universität Heidelberg, Im Neuenheimer Feld 253, D-69120 Heidelberg, Germany*

⁶*Present address: College of Chemistry, Nanchang University, Nanchang 330031, People's Republic of China*

**e-mail: r.c.chiechi@rug.nl, h.s.j.vanderzant@tudelft.nl*

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1 Experimental details

1.1 Synthesis and Characterization

Figure S1: Synthetic route for TC

Synthesis of 5,12-dimethoxy-5,12-bis((trimethylsilyl)ethynyl)-5,12-dihydrotetracene, **2**

In a dry three-neck flask under N₂, 3.2 mL of trimethylsilylacetylene (22.3 mmol) were dissolved in 40 mL of anhydrous THF and the solution was cooled to –70 °C with a EtOH/dry ice bath. 13.8 mL of *n*-butyllithium 1.6 M in hexane (22 mmol) was added drop-wise and the solution was stirred for 30 min in the cold bath. 1 g of tetracene-5,12-quinone (**1**, 4.4 mmol) was added. It slowly dissolved to form a yellowish solution. The mixture was allowed to warm to 0 °C, then the bath was removed and reaction kept under stirring for 3 hours. MeI (5.5 mL, 88 mmol) was added and the reaction heated to 50 °C overnight. After cooling to the room temperature, the mixture was poured into a saturated NH₄Cl solution. The aqueous phase was extracted with DCM, and the organic phases combined dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. Then, the solvent was evaporated by rotary evaporation. The crude solid was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, hexane:ethyl acetate 4:1) to obtain the product (856 mg, yield:40%). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃). δ: 8.47 (s, 2H), 8.05-7.99 (m, 2H), 7.98-7.93 (m, 2H), 7.58-7.53 (m, 2H), 7.52-7.49 (m, 2H), 2.90 (s, 6H), 0.17 (s, 18H).

Synthesis of 5,12-diethynyl-5,12-dimethoxy-5,12-dihydrotetracene, **3**

In a round bottom flask, 376 mg of K₂CO₃ (2.7 mmol) were added to a solution of **2** (856 mg, 1.8 mmol) in 100 mL of degassed methanol. The flask was stirred at room temperature under N₂ overnight. The solution was then poured into 100 mL water, extracted with DCM, and it was washed with saturated NaHCO₃, water and finally brine. The organic phase was then dried over Na₂SO₄

and the solvent removed by rotary evaporation to provide the product **3** as a solid in (582 mg, yield: 96 %). The crude was used in next step without further purification. $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3). δ : 8.50 (s, 2H), 8.09-8.02 (m, 2H), 8.01-7.94 (m, 2H), 7.59-7.49 (m, 4H), 2.93 (s, 6H), 2.84 (s, 2H).

Synthesis of S,S'-((tetracene-5,12-diylbis(ethyne-2,1-diyl))bis(4,1-phenylene)) diethanethioate, TC

In a dry Schlenk, 164 mg of **3** (0.48 mmol) and 404 mg of 4-ethynyl-1-thioacetylbenzene (1.45 mmol) were dissolved in mixture of freshly distilled Et_3N (3 mL) and anhydrous THF (10 mL) and the solution was degassed with N_2 . 23 mg of $\text{Pd}(\text{PPh}_3)_4$ (0.02 mmol) and 10 mg of CuI (0.05 mmol) were added. The reaction mixture was heated to 45 °C overnight. After that, 50 mL of a 10 % H_2SO_4 solution containing 11 g of SnCl_2 were added into the reaction mixture and stirred for one hour in the dark. The reaction was then poured into water (100 mL) the precipitate was collected by filtering and washed with MeOH. The crude solid was purified by recrystallization from MeOH and CHCl_3 to give the pure product as a red/purple solid (856 mg, yield:40 %). $^1\text{H NMR}$ (400 MHz, CDCl_3) δ : 9.22 (s, 2H), 8.67-8.56 (m, 2H), 8.15-8.05 (m, 2H), 7.90-7.81 (m, 4H), 7.61-7.48 (m, 8H), 2.49 (s, 6H).

Figure S2: Synthetic route for PC

Synthesis of 6,13-dimethoxy-6,13-bis((trimethylsilyl)ethynyl)-6,13-dihydropentacene, **5**

In a dry three-neck flask under N_2 , 1.45 mL of trimethylsilylacetylene (10.2 mmol) were dissolved in 50 mL of anhydrous THF and the solution was cooled to $-78\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ with a EtOH/dry ice bath. 6.25 mL of *n*-butyllithium 1.6 M in hexane (10 mmol) were added drop-wise and the solution stirred for 45 min. 611 mg of pentacene-6,13-quinone (**4**, 2 mmol) were added, and the mixture was slowly allowed to $0\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The bath was removed and reaction was keep stirring for 3 hour. MeI (7.5 mL

40 mmol) was added and the reaction was heated to 50 °C for two days. After cooling to room temperature, the mixture was poured into a saturated NH₄Cl aqueous solution. The aqueous phase was extracted with DCM, and the combined organic phases dried over anhydrous Na₂SO₄. The solvent was evaporated by rotary evaporation and the obtained product purified by column chromatography (silica gel, DCM:hexane 2:1) (482 mg, yield: 45 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 8.51 (s, 4H), 8.01-7.93 (m, 4H), 7.60-7.51 (m, 4H), 3.00 (s, 6H), 0.22 (s, 18H).

Synthesis of 6,13-diethynyl-6,13-dimethoxy-6,13-dihydropentacene, 6

In a round bottom flask under N₂, 120 mg of K₂CO₃ were added to a degassed solution of **5** (430 mg, 0.83 mmol) in THF-methanol (25 mL:25 mL). The solution was stirred at room temperature for one hour. It was then poured in water (100 mL), extracted with DCM, and the organic phase washed with saturated NaHCO₃, water and finally brine. The organic phase was then dried over Na₂SO₄ and the solvents removed by rotary evaporation to provide the product as a solid (218 mg, yield: 68 %). The crude was used in next step without further purification. ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 8.54 (s, 4H), 8.01-7.93 (m, 4H), 7.60-7.51 (m, 4H), 3.03 (s, 4H), 2.93 (s, 4H).

Synthesis of S,S'-((pentacene-6,13-diylbis(ethyne-2,1-diyl))bis(4,1-phenylene)) diethanethioate, PC

In a dry Schlenk flask under N₂, 125 mg of **6** (0.36 mmol) and 176 mg 4-ethynyl-1-thioacetylbenzene (1 mmol) were dissolved in mixture of fresh distilled Et₃N (5 mL) and anhydrous THF (10 mL). The solution was degassed and 58 mg of Pd(PPh₃)₄ (0.05 mmol) and 10 mg of CuI (0.05 mmol) were added. The reaction mixture was kept at 80 °C overnight. 50 mL of a 10 % H₂SO₄ solution containing 11 g of SnCl₂ were added into the reaction mixture and kept under stirring for one hour in the dark. The reaction was then poured into water (100 mL), extracted with DCM, and the organic phase washed with saturated NaHCO₃, water and finally brine. The organic phase was then dried over Na₂SO₄ and the solvents removed by rotary evaporation. The crude solid was purified by column chromatography (silica gel, DCM:hexane 1:2) to give the product as a dark blue solid (20 mg, yield: 27 %). ¹H NMR (400 MHz, CDCl₃) δ: 9.16 (s, 4H), 8.04-7.96 (m, 4H), 7.94-7.86 (m, 4H), 7.61-7.56 (m, 4H), 7.46-7.39 (m, 4H) 2.51 (s, 6H).

1.2 Preparation of SAMs

The Au substrates were prepared by template stripping (TS) described in details elsewhere.¹ 100 nm of Au (99.99%) were deposited by thermal deposition at 10⁻⁷ mbar onto a 3" Silicon wafer (without adhesion layer). Glass substrates (1 cm × 1 cm) were glued onto deposited metal by using UV-curable optical adhesive (Norland 61) with 300 s exposure of UV. All SAMs were formed by

incubating the thioacetate precursors with $1\text{ cm} \times 1\text{ cm}$ template-stripped Au surfaces (100 nm-thick) overnight in 3 mL of 50 μM solution of the respective compound in freshly distilled toluene followed by addition of 0.05 mL of 17 mmol dm^{-3} diazabicycloundec-7-ene solution in toluene 1 h prior the measurement. The substrates were then rinsed with ethanol and let to dry for 10 min.

1.3 EGaIn measurements

The raw data acquired using EGaIn are processed using Scientific Python. The source code is available at <http://github.com/rchiechi/GaussFit> and it retained internally in accordance with the aforementioned data retention policies. J-V curves and NDC plot are obtained directly from the code stated above. Low-bias conductance were obtained by computing the slope of EGaIn data (J vs. V) for the lowest 4 data points, *i.e.*, from -1 V to 1 V . This was done by fitting a linear equation to the linear $J - V$ data. Figure S3 is an example of the J/V data of **PC** junctions. The pink area is 95% confidential interval band, where the mean value and error bars of Low bias G are obtained by computing the largest value and lowest value of the slope of fitted line that is within this area.

Figure S3: An example: the 95% confidence band of the lowest 4 data points of J-V data of **PC** junctions

1.4 MCBJ measurement

A reference-free clustering algorithm was used to cluster the data. The method was detailed in previous work.² The noteworthy difference is on the definition of the feature vector. In this work, a 25x32 pixels image of the 2D-histogram was used. The displacement range was from -0.5 nm to 3 nm, and the conductance range was from -0.5 to $-6 \log(G/G_0)$ (the -0.5 limit being the point used for trace alignment). Additionally, the 1D conductance histogram, using 100 bins, was appended to the feature vector created from the image, for a total of 900 dimensions per trace. Each measurement was analysed individually, and the number of clusters was chosen to be the lowest that would isolate the high-conductance class (Table S1). Clusters showing only empty traces were merged together (when more than one would result from the analysis), and reported as the "empty class". All clusters showing molecular traces are reported without additional merging or sub-splitting, and in all measurement this resulted in one high-conductance class and one low-conductance class (in

some cases with multiple features). Additional analysis of the molecular features may reveal clearer low-conductance features, or hidden ones. However, this lies outside the scope of this work. The logarithmically binned 1D-conductance histograms were fitted using a Normal distribution, both for the raw data and for the molecular classes resulting from clustering. The position of the maximum of the fit is reported as the most-probable conductance value (or "conductance" for short) of the plateau. In the case of the raw data, a single Gaussian was used to fit the highest conductance peak exclusively, and the same holds for the high-conductance classes. Regarding low-conductance features, two Gaussians were used for the fit in cases where two peaks/plateaus were evident in both the 1D- and 2D- histograms. Otherwise, a single Gaussian distribution was employed. The histograms of the data and the resulting clusters are shown in Figure S4 (for **OPE3**), Figure S5 (for **NP**), Figure S6 and Figure S7 (for **AC**), Figure S8 (for **TC**), Figure S9 (for **PC**). The resulting fitting parameters are reported in Table S2 (raw data), Table S3 (high-conductance class), Table S4 (low-conductance features).

Table S1: Number of clusters used for each measurement.

Molecule	Measurement	Total clusters	Tunnelling clusters
OPE3	1	3	1
	2	3	1
NP	1	3	1
	2	3	1
	3	3	1
9,10-AC	1	3	1
	2	3	1
	3	4	2
	4	3	1
TC	1	3	1
	2	3	1
	3	5	3
PC	1	4	2
	2	4	2

Table S2: Conductance values and FWHM extracted from fitting the raw data of each measurement.

Molecule	Measurement	Conductance [G_0]	FWHM [decades]	N° traces
OPE3	1	6.3×10^{-5}	1.4	10000
	2	8.9×10^{-5}	1.2	10000
NP	1	1.0×10^{-4}	1.2	10000
	2	1.4×10^{-4}	1.1	10000
	3	9.7×10^{-5}	1.2	10000
9,10-AC	1	3.7×10^{-4}	0.8	10000
	2	3.9×10^{-4}	1.0	10000
	3	1.6×10^{-4}	1.2	10000
	4	3.0×10^{-4}	1.0	10000
TC	1	2.5×10^{-4}	1.0	10000
	2	2.4×10^{-4}	1.1	10000
	3	1.4×10^{-4}	1.3	10000
PC	1	4.0×10^{-4}	1.1	7324
	2	3.0×10^{-4}	1.5	7182

Table S3: Conductance values and FWHM extracted from fitting the high-conductance class for each measurement.

Molecule	Measurement	Conductance [G_0]	FWHM [decades]	Yield [%]
OPE3	1	9.4×10^{-5}	1.1	22
	2	9.5×10^{-5}	1.2	17
NP	1	1.2×10^{-4}	1.1	22
	2	1.5×10^{-4}	1.1	26
	3	1.3×10^{-4}	1.0	21
9,10-AC	1	4.1×10^{-4}	0.8	20
	2	3.6×10^{-4}	1.1	23
	3	2.4×10^{-4}	1.0	3
	4	4.3×10^{-4}	0.7	15
TC	1	3.7×10^{-4}	0.9	6
	2	2.8×10^{-4}	0.9	14
	3	2.8×10^{-4}	1.0	6
PC	1	5.5×10^{-4}	1.0	6
	2	5.0×10^{-4}	1.0	6

Table S4: Conductance values and FWHM extracted from fitting the low-conductance class for each measurement.

Molecule	Measurement	Conductance 1 [G_0]	FWHM 1 [decades]	Conductance 2 [G_0]	FWHM 2 [decades]	Yield [%]
OPE3	1			5.4×10^{-6}	1.9	16
	2			2.2×10^{-6}	1.7	17
NP	1	3.5×10^{-5}	0.8	2.2×10^{-6}	2.8	33
	2			1.6×10^{-6}	1.9	20
	3	2.7×10^{-5}	1.0	2.8×10^{-6}	3.0	25
9,10-AC	1	2.4×10^{-5}	1.2	2.0×10^{-6}	2.4	19
	2	2.2×10^{-5}	1.4	9.4×10^{-7}	3.7	30
	3					*
	4	4.0×10^{-5}	1.3			28
TC	1	4.3×10^{-5}	1.3			20
	2	2.1×10^{-5}	1.7			18
	3	4.5×10^{-5}	1.3			11
PC	1			1.0×10^{-5}	1.0	7
	2			5.6×10^{-6}	2.4	13

Conductance 1/FWHM 1 refer to $\approx 10^{-5}$ peaks, Conductance 2/FWHM 2 to $\approx 10^{-6}$ ones.

*Measurement 3 of AC had few low conductance molecular traces.

The class comprises mostly empty traces. Fitting was not possible.

Figure S4: 2D conductance-displacement and 1D conductance histograms of **OPE3** Measurements. Raw data is shown together with the classes resulting from the clustering analysis

Figure S5: 2D conductance-displacement and 1D conductance histograms of NP Measurements. Raw data is shown together with the classes resulting from the clustering analysis

Figure S6: 2D conductance-displacement and 1D conductance histograms of **9,10-AC** Measurements. Raw data is shown together with the classes resulting from the clustering analysis

Figure S7: 2D conductance-displacement and 1D conductance histograms of additional **9,10-AC** Measurements. Raw data is shown together with the classes resulting from the clustering analysis. *Measurement 3 of AC had extremely few low conductance molecular traces, the class is still largely composed of empty traces, for this reason fitting was not possible.

Figure S8: 2D conductance-displacement and 1D conductance histograms of TC Measurements. Raw data is shown together with the classes resulting from the clustering analysis

Figure S9: 2D conductance-displacement and 1D conductance histograms of **PC** Measurements. Raw data is shown together with the classes resulting from the clustering analysis

2 Characterization of the SAMs

2.1 Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) measurements

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Figure S10: AFM images of the SAMs of **OPE3**, **NP**, **9,10-AC**, **TC** and **PC** on Au^{TS}.

2.2 Angle-resolved XPS thickness measurement

Angle-resolved XPS (ARXPS) measurement were performed using a VG Microtech spectrometer with a hemispherical electron analyzer (Clam 100), and a MgK α (1253.6 eV) X-ray source. Operation of the measurement and Data analysis are following the method stated in the experimental section in a previous paper.³ Here we only pointed out the different part from that paper. The Au 4f peaks and C 2p were acquired with the sample rotated under 0, 5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 40 and 50 degrees with respect to the electron analyzer. An expression for the intensity of the peaks for different lengths of the path that through the overlayer:

$$I(\phi) = I_0 \exp\left(\frac{-L}{\phi}\right) = I_0 \exp\left(\frac{-d}{\lambda \cos(\phi)}\right) \quad (\text{S1})$$

with L the length of the path through the layer, d the thickness of the layer, λ the inelastic mean free path, ϕ the angle of rotation of the sample with respect to the analyzer, I_0 is the corrected peak intensity. The corrected peak intensity I^* are obtained by the $I^* = \gamma_1 I$ and can be used to determine the thickness of the layer. In the measurement, **C18SH** is used as the reference whose length is known as $(20.9 \pm 0.2) \text{ \AA}$.⁴ Then the λ value can be calculated. Next we can make a fit to the corrected intensities to find the thickness of the five Acene SAMs. Some of the samples indicated the presence of residual DBU from the in situ deprotection during the growth of the SAMs that increased the apparent thickness of the SAM slightly. These trace amounts of DBU do not impact the EGaIn measurements because they occur infrequently and randomly and, because we

Table S5: Effective thickness of SAMs of Acene molecules on Au surface (Au^{TS}) by angle-resolved XPS

	thickness(Å)	packing density (molecules/cm ²)±10%
SC18	20.9 ± 0.2	4.63 × 10 ¹⁴
OPE3	24.8 ± 2.3	3.5 × 10 ¹⁴ *
NP	21.0 ± 1.7	3.0 × 10 ¹⁴
9,10-AC	34.9 ± 4.5	2.9 × 10 ¹⁴
TC	26.4 ± 1.9	2.2 × 10 ¹⁴
PC	26.8 ± 2.1	2.9 × 10 ¹⁴

* This value is from our earlier work in reference⁵

measure many junctions across many substrates, they show up as low-frequency outliers in the conductance histograms; however, they are over-represented in the AR-XPS because we measured fewer substrates and XPS is very sensitive to small amounts of impurities. We do not know the cause of the residual DBU, as it appears to be unique to the acene series.

2.3 Synchrotron-Based X-ray Photoelectron Spectroscopy (XPS)

The spectra were fitted by symmetric Voigt functions and a linear or Shirley-type background. The S 2p spectra were decomposed by several S 2p_{3/2,1/2} doublets. Each of these doublets comprised two peaks with the same full width at half-maximum, a standard⁶ spin-orbit splitting of ~ 1.2 eV (verified by fit), and a branching ratio of 2 ($S2p_{3/2}/S2p_{1/2}$). The packing densities of the monolayers were calculated from the $S2p/Au4f$ intensity ratio,⁷ with the thiolate signal only being taking into account. A standard exponential attenuation of the photoelectron signal was assumed⁸ and the attenuation lengths typical of densely packed SAMs were used.⁹ An octadecanethiolate (SC18) SAM with a well defined packing density ($4.63 \times 10^{14} \text{ cm}^{-2}$)⁴ served as the reference, to

determine the spectrometer-specific constants.

3 Relating Packing to Conductance

3.1 Low-bias Conductance in SAMs

In order to make it clear that conductance behavior of **PC** SAM is quite different among the Acene series, we also calculated the conductance of individual molecules at low bias by using data from EGaIn measurement and HRXPS measurement (Figure S11). The conductance of individual molecule is calculated by using the formula:

$$G/molecule = \frac{(dJ/dV) \times A_{eff}}{\rho \times A_{eff}} \quad (S2)$$

dJ/dV is obtained from the EGaIn measurement at low bias, the details are stated above in section 2.3. A_{eff} is the effective contact area between EGaIn tip and the substrate. $A_{eff} = \chi_0 \times A$ (A is the real contact area, which is defined by the diameter of the tip, χ_0 is the correction factor of effective contact area). In this case, A_{eff} can be easily leaved out as it showed up both in the numerator and denominator. Packing density ρ is obtained from XPS and is listed in Table S5.

Figure S11: Conductance of individual molecule at low bias calculated from EGaIn measurement. The value of conductance of **PC** is lower than the other four molecules.

3.2 Qualitative Description of Packing

Figure S12 is a top-down view showing how intermolecular interaction might develop in the Acene series on Au(111) substrate. The lattice distance a is $2.88 \text{ \AA}$ and the S-S distance is $\sqrt{3}a$. The colored circles represent axial benzene rings and the intersecting lines show the width of the perpendicular acene functionality. Based on that the value of packing density of the five SAMs shows no big difference (Table S5), here we arranged same amount of each molecules in the Au surface within the same-sized gold surface. We see that OPE3, NP and 9,10-AC can be packed freely while TC and PC lost some freedoms. Figure S12 also shows two types of TC SAMs (d,e) and two types of PC SAMs (f,g). Type d and type f are less favored arrangement as the inter-molecule interactions between aromatic rings would be big. Type e and type g are energetically favored but defects and vacancies would be increased. Since the packing density of SAMs are similar, so we assumes that

there might be a competition among the two types of arrangement within the SAMs. Aso PC SAMs needs more type f, as compared the needs of type d in TC SAMs, to compensate the defects in the type g.

Figure S12: A top-down view showing how intermolecular interactions might develop in the acene series Au (111). The lattice distance a is $2.88 \text{ \AA}$ and the S-S distance is $\sqrt{3}a$. The colored circles represent axial benzene rings and the intersecting lines show the width of the perpendicular acene functionality showing: a) OPE3 SAMs, b) NP SAMs, c) 9,10-AC SAMs, d) and e) two types of TC SAMs, f) and g) two types of PC SAMs.

3.3 Thin-area Defect Model

The assumption of the possible competition of the two types of arrangement of TC and PC molecules existing in SAMs gives us a possible explanation of why we only see significantly suppressed conductance features in PC but not TC in EGaIn measurements. A simple model for tunneling transport SAMs in which a fraction of the molecules in the SAM is less resistive to tunneling currents, is to model the total current using the simplified Simmons equation, $J = J_0 e^{-\beta d}$ where d is the effective tunneling distance, β is the tunneling decay coefficient and J_0 is the theoretical value of at $d = 0$. To describe areas of the SAM that are more conductive, d is varied to account for a change in the effective width of the tunneling barrier, while leaving β constant. These areas are, therefore, called “thin-area defects,” but can be used to describe any region of a SAM that exhibits a smaller effective tunneling distance, *i.e.*, some fraction of molecules that are more conductive than the rest of the SAM.^{10,11} Equation S3 is used to describe the current density J_{total} where χ is the fraction of thin-area defects (more conductive molecules) and J_i is the nominal current density of the pristine SAM.

$$J_{total} = \chi J_0 e^{-\beta d} + (1 - \chi) J_i \quad (S3)$$

In our case we assume that π - π stacked geometry (Figure S12 d,f) leads to lower conductance, while geometries lacking π - π contacts (Figure S12 g,e) leads to higher conductance. We took the low-conductance value from MCBJ results as J_i , values of J_0 and β from series of OPEs,¹²

and d as the theoretical length of acene molecules to plot J_{total} as a function of the percentage of J_{total} carried by $\pi - \pi$ -stacked molecules in Figure S13. We also varied the effective tunneling distance as a percentage of the theoretical length to consider defects and impurities in the SAM. The thin-area defect model is normally applied to SAMs that exhibit higher than expected conductances because only a small fraction of highly-conductive molecules is required to increase the total conductance of the junction. This behavior is evident in Figure S13, which shows that SAMs of both TC and PC require very large fractions of molecules to adopt a π - π -stacked geometry to affect the total conductance of the junction because, in our case, the “thin-area defects” are molecules that are packed normally and not π -stacked. The dashed lines in Figure S13 are the current density values at 0.1 V from our EGaIn junctions, which predict that the observed junction conductance can only be driven by π -stacking in SAMs of PC and that the fraction of molecules that engage in stacking must be close to 100 %.

Figure S13: Plots of Equation S3 with x axis is $(1 - \chi)$, J_i is the low conductance value of TC and PC from MCBJ (see Table S4), $J_0 = 10^{-0.3} \text{Acm}^{-2}$ and $\beta = 0.23 \text{ \AA}$ from literature.¹² The percentages refer to the defects or impurities as compared to the theoretical length of OPE3 of $20.27 \text{ \AA}$. The horizontal dashed lines indicate the experimental value of J_{total} at 0.1 bias from EGaIn measurements.

Table S6: Energy level obtained from DFT calculations

Molecules	HOMO(eV)	LUMO(eV)	E_g (eV)
OPE3	-5.48	-2.05	3.43
NP	-5.34	-2.28	3.06
9,10-AC	-5.07	-2.60	2.47
TC	-4.89	-2.82	2.07
PC	-4.70	-3.02	1.68

4 Computational details

4.1 simulation results

Figure S14: Simulated I/V curves, replotted from transmission curves.

Figure S15: Simulated NDC plot, replotted from transmission curves.

Figure S16: Frontier Molecular Orbitals: HOMO and LUMO for the acene series molecules.

Slip-stack transmission calculations. We simulated the ideal metal-molecule-metal junctions using the *BAND* module of Amsterdam Density Functional (ADF) quantum chemistry program for the pentacene molecular wire. We performed this simulations for a single wire between electrodes and two wires in slip-stack conformation using ADF-BAND implements Non-Equilibrium Green's Function approach with DFT¹³⁻¹⁷ as shown in Figure S17. This quantum chemistry code uses localized basis-functions that are Slater-type or numerical atomic orbital type.

We optimized the single and dimer pentacene molecular wire using GGA:PBE functional and *TZ2P* basis sets. As can be seen in Figure S17, we optimized the single wire with two Au atoms attached to the two thiols, and single Au atoms attached two the opposite thiols in case of the dimer. Due to the presence of the gold atoms, we used ZORA scalar relativistic effects with DZ basis sets for Au and TZ2P for the rest of the atoms. This Au atoms served as reference point for attachment to the electrodes in the NEGF calculations. We also included dispersion corrections for the dimer by using GGA:PBED3 functional instead of GGA:PBE functional to account for accurate calculation of the $\pi - \pi$ interactions between the two wires. and two pentacene wires with thiol as the terminal group. Coordinates of all the optimized geometries are shown in subsection 4.2.

Figure S17: Optimized geometries of petacene molecular wire (left) and the slip-stacked dimer (right) from ADF calculations

The optimized geometries were connected to two leads consisting of gold electrodes in Au111 arrangement. The two Au atoms that were attached to thiols in the optimized geometry served as the tip of the two leads. The two leads and molecule formed the *extended molecule* system which is finite. The leads then connect to two semi-infinite, periodic electrodes. *Self-consistent* method for determining fermi level was used in BAND module implementing NEGF with DFT. We used *SZ* basis set and *GGA:PBE* functional with scalar *ZORA* relativistic effects. 5 layers of gold atoms were used in the electrodes. Calculations were also performed on systems with 3 and 4 layers of Au layers to check for convergence of transmission as suggested by the BAND authors. This entire conformation is shown in Figure S18.

Figure S18: Schematic of junction geometries of the two structures in Figure S17 showing the *semi-infinite, periodic electrode-left lead-molecule-right lead-semi infinite, periodic electrode* configuration for single and dimer pentacene molecule.

The generated transmission spectra are shown in Figure S19. The transmission spectrum of the pentacene molecular wire exhibits same shape as from orca calculation in the main text. The shape near E_f is bowl-shaped while the two QI dips occur after the transmission *peaks*. The dimer, however, shows suppressed transmission in gaps and broadened QI features, suggesting that in this slip-stack geometry the conductance of these junctions would be lower than the junction with only one molecule trapped.

Figure S19: Transmission spectra for single and dimer pentacene molecular wires shown in black and red, respectively. The transmission of the dimer reduces all over in the energy window near the fermi level, broadening the destructive QI peaks.

We also computed the *single-point energies* of these two optimized geometries (molecules with two Au atoms at the opposite sulfur groups) using **Hybrid:B3LYP-D3** functional (to account for van der Waal interactions) and *TZ2P* (triple-zeta with two polarization functions) basis sets. We used one-component scalar ZORA relativistic effects without any frozen core approximations. The isoplots of obtained frontier orbitals with energies is shown in Figure S20. (We exclude the levels with orbital density majorly localized on the Au atoms.)

QI prediction with Orbital coefficients: Figure S20 shows a table at the bottom listing the product of orbital coefficients for both the mono and dimer pentacene geometries with Au atoms attached. A -1 product means that the orbital coefficients are different on the either ends of molecular orbital, while a $+1$ means that the orbital coefficients are the same. As it can be seen from the table, the orbital coefficient product is same for HOMO and LUMO+1 and for HOMO-1 and LUMO, only in the case for the dimer configuration. This is the same as in the case of meta-connected benzenedithiol molecules, as discussed earlier in a book chapter by Gemma *et al.*¹⁸

Figure S20: HOMO, HOMO–1, LUMO, and LUMO+1 isoplots of single pentacene and dimer with two Au atoms attached to each of the systems on the opposite thiols. The geometry is shown on the top. These were calculated using ADF at *Hybrid:B3LYP-D3* and *TZP* level. At the bottom of the figure is a table listing the product of orbital coefficients at the terminal sulfur group for every orbital.

4.2 Coordinates of Optimized Geometries

ORCA optimized OPE3 molecule:

H -2.43550480449032 9.74084532664743 -2.83927892398352
S -3.60412099321343 9.04213002740569 -2.82556644719044
H -4.86378856793552 6.51987845906418 -2.35621188453909
C -2.90542352397701 7.48542025990584 -2.32800933573380
H -0.82295979319514 8.13413689410902 -2.20118763002704
C -3.78625464053792 6.38885404739780 -2.17082839235103
C -1.52593724081540 7.29451153006902 -2.08476822370053
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C -1.04071570688533 6.04274385428268 -1.69540640958267
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H 0.03523455728096 5.90871968811016 -1.50951445689800
C -1.41952870850596 3.65933272895134 -1.13763628211782
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C -0.89097631543838 -1.07708228602134 0.15119662455345
C 1.37515865844672 -0.17142306298944 0.23792365856597
H -1.58364867074430 -1.92326584072703 0.27070933408462
C 0.49632024721288 -1.27992218005550 0.39848856420389
H 2.45011928713458 -0.31116011480590 0.42508263072364
C 0.99034168475145 -2.55359629311906 0.79458913139463
C 1.41950142440743 -3.65912868470477 1.13842654751156
H -0.03527408456937 -5.90850129252363 1.51033898973394
C 1.91475424253291 -4.93322912845545 1.53483622338149
H 3.99615290752095 -4.29466518438528 1.66418486170226
C 1.04067409110537 -6.04252660905634 1.69624305404608
C 3.30041285426485 -5.13843987359895 1.78261596188696
C 1.52588694351755 -7.29428830006158 2.08563455129847
C 3.78620809405284 -6.38864019703863 2.17169452227314
H 0.82290540889103 -8.13390861752545 2.20206400680262
C 2.90537031865670 -7.48519853166296 2.32889192943586

H 4.86373971096327 -6.51966500631506 2.35709006877161
S 3.60405574739702 -9.04190125046624 2.82648711523556
H 2.43543539447094 -9.74060954746729 2.84020724744542

ORCA optimized NP molecule:

H 0.04333925290248 4.36420852162349 -9.41962609773033
S -1.13055767466380 3.67520715321698 -9.45617676287955
H -2.91031547637370 1.92912786237307 -8.05725439708462
C -1.00205923694594 2.96664397659743 -7.83149691506283
C -2.05243217842336 2.12450531716619 -7.39511745664243
H 0.91777865519769 3.85509353210227 -7.28321727008328
C 0.08947194753624 3.20321594569568 -6.96448269661997
C -2.01135048804335 1.53706148069459 -6.12885494952532
H -2.83471437192906 0.88455672897142 -5.80277317922942
C 0.12963972036893 2.61467131363085 -5.69745424776619
C -0.91904943886507 1.76690212085826 -5.24660135592452
H 0.98579737480920 2.80881666871290 -5.03458649365209
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H 0.71989854488751 -2.36093362305409 5.40856234745815

C -1.18315994243954 -3.10322187237677 4.64232344155404
H -3.11366746444701 -4.02204904786966 4.21168759090490
C -0.16310420099850 -2.97972582284339 5.62628466386622
C -2.31114699250734 -3.91057079791280 4.95580401263586
C -0.26556043041647 -3.62922263650394 6.85831234306690
C -2.41484304710407 -4.56099752015543 6.18838430475521
H 0.53944495361419 -3.51578810442130 7.60103331178718
C -1.39362263455172 -4.42972203996697 7.15752688757276
H -3.30157137483133 -5.17884146158634 6.39962563348184
S -1.44769239536913 -5.22153398475989 8.74749168097028
H -2.64771362225447 -5.84087198912284 8.57308076096777

ORCA optimized 910-AC molecule:

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C -1.07895259835752 0.86258593847707 -0.39824890308731
C -2.16074681209101 1.72999960792955 -0.75419184736254
H -2.38914801740509 1.86208012802257 -1.82174261607773
C -2.90395727481417 2.38820364604474 0.21054400281931
S 2.22053652753006 -1.34268794435463 9.80926833344191
H 0.11893853743916 0.31367910619077 8.47109326574651
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H 0.40641784690610 -0.62801250452973 -6.06744594334718
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H -3.35761432114278 2.39262821680316 -7.40807197432356
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ORCA optimized TC molecule:

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ORCA optimized PC molecule:

C -0.30597710663698 0.18094135591819 -1.40583977582985
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C -4.70273369924547 3.97827751683765 0.80008586975461
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H -0.13693723302473 -0.34998428753022 -8.47254204615729
S -2.22627772944528 1.31898115668951 -9.81377093237612
H -3.35089440050194 2.39169499238186 -7.41498585731799
H -2.81832857324358 2.08153262814752 -5.00894082025690
H 1.28863317177025 -0.49817537144718 10.35618726852396
H -1.28301666354347 0.50096147369537 -10.35709515830904

ADF optimized pentacene with two Au atoms:

C -0.01705719530582428 -1.344628214836121 0.615031898021698
C 0.1126197874546051 1.39495849609375 -0.2546592354774475
C -1.157431244850159 0.7484068870544434 -0.1196825429797173
C -1.222731590270996 -0.6323506236076355 0.3161968290805817
C 3.694288015365601 -0.7400233745574951 0.7105021476745605
C 3.759384870529175 0.640073299407959 0.2773875296115875
C 2.575036525726318 1.308820605278015 -0.03110339306294918

C 1.316933035850525 0.6897839903831482 0.06660044938325882
C 1.251421093940735 -0.6896973848342896 0.5058602690696716
C 2.448921918869019 -1.359930753707886 0.8098554015159607
C -2.355902910232544 1.42302143573761 -0.4101059436798096
C -2.482321739196777 -1.244021058082581 0.4379775524139404
C 4.912489891052246 -1.418125748634338 1.02252459526062
C 5.038689613342285 1.26889705657959 0.1820192635059357
H 2.619242668151855 2.349103689193726 -0.3556145429611206
C -3.602823972702026 0.8105260133743286 -0.286435455083847
C -3.668260097503662 -0.5678657293319702 0.1525546014308929
C -4.822611808776855 1.495226979255676 -0.5773868560791016
C -4.949653625488281 -1.187028527259827 0.2786698639392853
C 0.1825875639915466 2.718889713287354 -0.7108102440834045
H -2.301681995391846 2.460451602935791 -0.742516815662384
H -2.526948213577271 -2.281518936157227 0.7714487314224243
H 2.395058631896973 -2.399646282196045 1.134882211685181
C 6.183459281921387 0.5819979310035706 0.4916423559188843
C 6.119525909423828 -0.7778359651565552 0.9163488149642944
H 4.862144470214844 -2.458653926849365 1.348239183425903
H 7.042328357696533 -1.306531548500061 1.157826781272888
H 7.154065608978271 1.073326945304871 0.4148717224597931
H 5.085805416107178 2.309904336929321 -0.142676830291748
C -6.0958571434021 -0.4936041235923767 -0.01039206795394421
C -6.031413555145264 0.8635317087173462 -0.4436175227165222
H -4.772034168243408 2.533869981765747 -0.9089525938034058
H -6.955413341522217 1.397313833236694 -0.6687727570533752
H -7.068079948425293 -0.9773865938186646 0.0902293473482132
H -4.997252464294434 -2.225479602813721 0.61134934425354
C -0.07765527814626694 -2.689004421234131 1.007859468460083
C -0.1284542828798294 -3.868968963623047 1.335279107093811
H 1.863588213920593 -5.312362670898438 2.402841329574585
C 0.258926659822464 3.869872331619263 -1.124973297119141
H -1.724077701568604 5.673038482666016 -1.340206503868103
C 0.3677351176738739 5.185410976409912 -1.617129445075989
C 1.61732017993927 5.686587810516357 -2.061046361923218
C 1.72799015045166 6.969606876373291 -2.56624698638916
C 0.6043962836265564 7.817809581756592 -2.626249551773071
C -0.6353452205657959 7.334268569946289 -2.165643692016602
C -0.7573848962783813 6.038277149200439 -1.686468243598938
H 2.492297887802124 5.038023948669434 -2.020054340362549
H 2.689192533493042 7.335911750793457 -2.926675796508789
S 0.6652204990386963 9.411020278930664 -3.382801294326782

H -1.503847002983093 7.992456436157227 -2.192676067352295
C -0.1837410926818848 -5.229543685913086 1.695735692977905
C -1.364647269248962 -5.983704566955566 1.507414937019348
C -1.404290080070496 -7.331145286560059 1.832946300506592
C -0.2804061472415924 -7.970030784606934 2.391146659851074
C 0.8944023847579956 -7.219458103179932 2.596494674682617
C 0.9482499361038208 -5.882492542266846 2.24471116065979
H -2.241888284683228 -5.499756336212158 1.078487396240234
H -2.310434818267822 -7.910935401916504 1.656852245330811
S -0.4393555223941803 -9.644563674926758 2.923834800720215
H 1.765164971351624 -7.70608377456665 3.035746574401855
Au 2.051103830337524 10.64143085479736 -2.095887422561646
Au 1.068200826644897 -10.81140232086182 1.717169761657715

ADF optimized pentacene dimer in slip-stacked geometry:

C -0.62260100 -1.32282300 2.72752300
C -0.51923300 1.45301400 1.99509000
C -1.78472100 0.80127400 2.14275100
C -1.83606600 -0.60139400 2.49784800
C 3.08688800 -0.72786900 2.72337800
C 3.14068200 0.66645700 2.33564400
C 1.94890900 1.35123500 2.09995200
C 0.69412200 0.73411400 2.23375100
C 0.64119100 -0.66418200 2.60899100
C 1.84503400 -1.34997400 2.84269500
C -2.99178100 1.49101500 1.94037900
C -3.08974900 -1.22957000 2.59987600
C 4.31284600 -1.41997700 2.96303400
C 4.41802800 1.28927400 2.19845700
H 1.98509300 2.39837300 1.79635300
C -4.23242000 0.86662800 2.05618500
C -4.28326200 -0.54244900 2.38485600
C -5.45918600 1.56603800 1.84657600
C -5.55886400 -1.17949500 2.47310200
C -0.47963100 2.79128400 1.58921700
H -2.95006200 2.54798100 1.67638600
H -3.12140400 -2.28962700 2.85530600
H 1.79832200 -2.40331300 3.12180000

C 5.57116600 0.58822900 2.43567900
C 5.51757800 -0.78216100 2.82388500
H 4.26917400 -2.47074200 3.25556000
H 6.44751700 -1.32311100 3.00127100
H 6.54051600 1.07199500 2.31418100
H 4.45635800 2.33534200 1.89004100
C -6.71319100 -0.47280400 2.25622000
C -6.66276100 0.91774100 1.94284400
H -5.41668300 2.62757100 1.59737300
H -7.59290500 1.46273900 1.77765100
H -7.68100100 -0.97070300 2.32701500
H -5.59539400 -2.24262800 2.71843700
C -0.67634600 -2.68133400 3.06734700
C -0.73516200 -3.86868500 3.35874500
H 1.30797100 -5.60423200 3.41329300
C -0.48580200 3.95055100 1.19432100
H -2.64428900 5.16022600 0.20534500
C -0.53896100 5.26749100 0.70695700
C 0.60664500 6.09622200 0.69327000
C 0.53436000 7.39341400 0.21258800
C -0.67376900 7.90623100 -0.29716900
C -1.81780300 7.08326500 -0.29195100
C -1.75631200 5.79317800 0.20474200
H 1.55055800 5.70089300 1.06755500
H 1.42024200 8.02807500 0.20604300
S -0.69046800 9.49951300 -1.05146300
H -2.75407500 7.47813900 -0.68665900
C -0.80858900 -5.23934700 3.67619600
C -2.04517100 -5.84708000 3.98967900
C -2.12260100 -7.20312400 4.26657700
C -0.96610900 -8.00170000 4.24774500
C 0.27051900 -7.40527400 3.95019700
C 0.34724400 -6.05105700 3.66658400
H -2.94888600 -5.23787900 4.00156900
H -3.09039200 -7.65527800 4.48718100
S -1.13741200 -9.71737300 4.62487600
H 1.17587600 -8.01189600 3.92602700
Au -1.73955400 10.85610500 0.48012700
H 0.04178400 -10.10499200 4.08348700
C 0.91941300 -1.22700600 -0.91492800
C 1.24133300 1.54350100 -1.60828500
C -0.06988000 0.98452700 -1.49729900

C -0.23357600 -0.41269100 -1.15182000
C 4.66668500 -0.90697500 -0.87389700
C 4.82863500 0.48390400 -1.24107300
C 3.69283800 1.25718300 -1.47628900
C 2.39410500 0.73058100 -1.37035200
C 2.23213700 -0.66370700 -1.01517500
C 3.38035700 -1.43547000 -0.77302000
C -1.21586500 1.77075300 -1.70665200
C -1.53356000 -0.93640800 -1.05288600
C 5.83410300 -1.68918200 -0.62163700
C 6.14981000 1.01680400 -1.33934800
H 3.80795400 2.30685300 -1.74993500
C -2.50253600 1.24633000 -1.60261400
C -2.66692000 -0.15399100 -1.27168500
C -3.66973900 2.04527700 -1.80448400
C -3.98997600 -0.68111300 -1.16695500
C 1.39978400 2.89179300 -1.95761700
H -1.08633000 2.82732300 -1.94401600
H -1.65361400 -1.98714900 -0.78623500
H 3.25436800 -2.48127400 -0.49089600
C 7.24462200 0.23108000 -1.08807400
C 7.08497300 -1.13867200 -0.72535000
H 5.70833600 -2.73564000 -0.33849100
H 7.96881200 -1.74679800 -0.52910900
H 8.24857000 0.65011700 -1.16664000
H 6.26988600 2.06556000 -1.61744000
C -5.08302500 0.11798000 -1.37503000
C -4.92133300 1.49773200 -1.69596900
H -3.54131500 3.10167800 -2.04898900
H -5.80570100 2.11718900 -1.84942700
H -6.08752200 -0.29411100 -1.27714800
H -4.11288200 -1.73298700 -0.90424300
C 0.76972800 -2.57952500 -0.59237100
C 0.65383100 -3.76832600 -0.31927700
H 2.68876000 -5.46895400 0.01042700
C 1.54232600 4.06419300 -2.27935100
H -0.35701000 5.69434200 -3.24648300
C 1.70615200 5.41139600 -2.65807900
C 2.96063800 6.05107500 -2.54222000
C 3.12300500 7.37775600 -2.91047300
C 2.03892900 8.11432100 -3.41686700
C 0.78547200 7.48841200 -3.53597400

C 0.62209200 6.16439900 -3.16098400
H 3.80942100 5.48949700 -2.15194200
H 4.10194600 7.84738100 -2.80610900
S 2.16552100 9.80177900 -3.91090700
H -0.06895200 8.04971800 -3.91558300
C 0.54683600 -5.13895300 -0.02907500
C -0.71425800 -5.76363800 0.10899000
C -0.80789200 -7.12224200 0.36511300
C 0.35144300 -7.90454100 0.52973300
C 1.61193500 -7.28690100 0.40168700
C 1.71013800 -5.93680100 0.11965300
H -1.61696300 -5.16200900 0.00615300
H -1.78418400 -7.59721600 0.45966400
S 0.17888300 -9.58885700 1.01426500
H 2.51143600 -7.89073100 0.52283400
H 3.48847600 9.93312900 -3.66093800
Au 1.05937300 -10.80483800 -0.72691700

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